

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Menglimamatova Rohila Raxmatillo qizi

HOMILADORLIK PAYTIDA PARAZITLARNING INSON TANASIGA TA'SIRI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/FEVRAL

